

With Paratransit Services to Participation in Daily Activities: The Experiences of Persons with Disabilities in Switzerland

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SUMMARY

Mobility is a human right, and transportation is crucial for enabling persons with disabilities to participate in daily activities, impacting their health and well-being. In Switzerland, paratransit services serve as an alternative to public transportation for persons with disabilities. Yet, their organization, availability, and funding differ regionally and lack a federal legal foundation. Therefore, the overall objectives of this thesis are to examine the experiences of persons with disabilities with paratransit services in Switzerland and to explore how these services influence their participation in daily activities. The specific aims are: 1) Examining the experiences and needs of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services; 2) Identifying the impact of paratransit services on participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities; and 3) Assessing the impact of per-trip costs and financing schemes for paratransit services on participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities.

My thesis employs a mixed-method exploratory sequential design, beginning with a qualitative study involving five focus groups, followed by a national cross-sectional survey leading to two quantitative studies. The results show that the impact of paratransit services on participation in daily activities is highly individual and influenced by personal and environmental factors. Paratransit services are vital for those without other transportation options, but barriers such as high-per-trip costs, particularly affect participation in leisure activities. This leads to transport-related social exclusion. The results of my thesis expand the knowledge on the adaptations needed to provide equal access to transportation for all.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Art.	Article
BTB	Foundation Disabled Transport Canton of Berne
CRPD	Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
DDA	Federal Act on the Elimination of Discrimination against People with Disabilities
EBGB	Federal Office for the Equality of Persons with Disabilities
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
FDFA	Federal Department of Foreign Affairs
ICF	International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health
Par.	Paragraph
UN	United Nations
WHO	World Health Organization
ZHAW	Zurich University of Applied Sciences

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

BACKGROUND

Transportation enables persons with disabilities to participate in daily activities, which improves health and well-being. Among the various transportation options, paratransit services are crucial especially when other transportation modes are inaccessible or limited. However, several barriers often limit these services. These barriers, such as inflexibility in use, high costs, and the absence of a robust legal foundation, not only restrict the usability and availability of paratransit services but also pose a risk of exacerbating transport-related social exclusion and undermining the fundamental rights of persons with disabilities.

Using transportation, participation, and health of persons with disabilities

To understand the impact of transportation on participation in the daily activities of persons with disabilities and the subsequent effect on health and well-being, we have to first establish four definitions: persons with disabilities, daily activities, using transportation, and participation. By referring to disability as the individual experience of environmental barriers such as inaccessible transportation rather than physical or mental impairments but recognizing the diversity of the individual experience of impairments, my thesis adopts the human rights model (1). This perspective, also adopted by the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), advocates for inclusion and extensive rights – human, civil, political, economic, social and cultural – of persons with disabilities (2). It advocates for legal and policy reforms to guarantee equal rights to persons with disabilities (2).

Secondly, we need to define what is meant by “daily activities”. In alignment with the definition of the World Health Organization (3), in this thesis, “daily activities” are tasks or actions such as work, leisure, or social interactions which are part of daily living. Thirdly, building on these definitions, the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) (3) emphasizes the integral relationship between mobility, transportation, and participation by categorizing “using transportation” as a subdomain of “mobility” and “activities and participation”. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) (3), mobility involves changing body positions or location, whereas “using transportation” specifically refers to “moving around as a passenger” by, for example, car, taxi, train, or aircraft.

Lastly, accessible transportation has a fundamental role in enabling persons with disabilities to participate in daily activities. Therefore, it becomes imperative to explore how this access influences broader concepts of participation. Derecik (4) presents a dual perspective on participation, differentiating between community/political and individual levels. The community/political level emphasizes involvement and influence in decision-making processes within parliaments, governments, and political parties as well as addressing societal challenges such as aging societies and global

competition through social innovation or intercultural communication (4). In contrast with the community/political level of participation, the individual level focuses on the subjective experience and satisfaction of participation (5,6). Here, participation is understood as a means of inclusion (4) or, according to the ICF, as involvement in a life situation (3). However, some authors argue that the ICF does not encompass the subjective experience of participation (7,8). Imms et al. (5) place greater emphasis on subjectivity, defining participation with the concepts of attendance (defined as being there) and involvement. They consider the latter as crucial for the experience of participation including motivation, persistence, social connection, and affect; these are viewed as indicators of engagement or interest in an activity. Their framework posits using transportation not only as a means to participate in daily activities but also as a participatory act in itself (e.g., feeling socially connected to other passengers during the trip). Therefore, in this thesis “using transportation” encompasses the experience of participation during its use and/or leading to participation in daily activities both on an individual or community/political level. This is measured through the subjective experience of participation. Given this understanding of participation, we need to explore its broader impacts, particularly on the health and wellbeing of persons with disabilities.

Transportation significantly contributes to the health and overall wellbeing of persons with disabilities (9–13). Suitable transportation modes can improve life satisfaction (14), foster a feeling of social inclusion (15–17), and increase self-efficacy (18). However, barriers such as inaccessible or unavailable transportation services can lead to unmet transportation needs, significantly impacting the health of persons with disabilities (9,11,12). Inadequate transportation options can cause mental and physical health issues for these individuals, including loneliness (19), social exclusion (18,20), stress (18), frustration, depression (21), and physical degradation (22). This interrelationship of transportation, participation in daily activities, and health shows the need for accessible and inclusive transportation systems for persons with disabilities.

Inclusive transportation systems create opportunities for all individuals accessing transportation (23). Such systems fulfill functional requirements such as accessibility, flexibility, safety, reliability, economic predictability, and other requirements such as provision, design, policy, and planning of transportation (24–28). Accessibility is defined by the United Nations (29) as the flexibility to accommodate any place, space, service or item to the needs and preferences of persons with disabilities. Overall, there is an increase in awareness and efforts for inclusive transportation systems (16,30,31). Despite these efforts, challenges with using public transportation modes for persons with disabilities persist. These are barriers such as inaccessible public spaces and service systems, lack of support and information, inadequate policies, and limited societal awareness towards these needs (32,33). If these barriers

prevent persons with disabilities from using public transportation, persons with disabilities must rely on other transportation modes such as assistance from friends and family, paratransit services, or personal vehicles, if feasible. Whether persons with disabilities can rely on these supplementary modes depends on their individual social network, socio-economic status, and health condition (15,34,35). In case these alternative modes are unavailable or inaccessible, persons with disabilities face the risk of involuntary transport disadvantage (36).

Transport disadvantage occurs if people have difficulty to travel if needed or if they can't participate in daily activities, a situation influenced by factors such as personal characteristics, their surroundings, and the accessibility of transportation systems (36,37). Such difficulties can lead to social exclusion, an involuntary (38), multilayered and dynamic (39) inability to participate in social, economic and political life (40). This process, where transport disadvantage leads to social exclusion, is referred to as "transport-related social exclusion" (41–44).

Furthermore, transport-related social exclusion has a negative effect on determinants of health such as social isolation and well-being (35,45) and persons with disabilities are, besides the elderly and adolescents, the group of people facing the highest risk of transport-related social exclusion (36).

Mobility rights of persons with disabilities

Various national and international laws address equal transportation options for persons with disabilities. Defining equal transportation, in alignment with the concept of inclusive equality by the United Nations (46), involves ensuring fair access to transportation; addressing socio-economic disadvantages; combating stigma, prejudice, stereotyping, and violence; recognizing the dignity and intersectionality of individuals; including persons with disabilities as full members of society; and creating space for differences as a matter of human dignity (47). Different international laws such as the UN Covenant I, UN Covenant II, and the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) grant equal mobility rights to persons with disabilities and oblige state parties to guarantee the rights proclaimed in these documents (48,49). While neither the UN Covenant I and II nor the ECHR mentions mobility rights explicitly, they implicitly encompass personal mobility as a prerequisite for realizing other guaranteed rights, such as the right to take part in cultural life or the right to education (49,50). Moreover, the CRPD aims to ensure all human rights for persons with disabilities (51). It highlights mobility rights in Articles 9 and 20. Article 9 calls for full participation and equal access to the physical environment and transportation modes (Par.1). Article 20 specifies the mobility rights as follows:

State parties shall take effective measures to ensure personal mobility with the greatest possible independence for [persons with disabilities] [...] by facilitating the personal

mobility [of persons with disabilities] in the manner and at the time of their choice, and at affordable costs (Art. 20).

Switzerland has ratified the UN-Covenants I and II as well as the CRPD, committing the nation to implementing these laws (52). However, these international agreements include optional protocols that enable complaint procedures, allowing individuals or groups to report a violation of these rights (53). Since Switzerland has not ratified these optional protocols, Swiss citizens are unable to claim the violation of the rights in these frameworks (52). Unlike the UN Covenants I and II and the CRPD, the ECHR encompasses rights that are directly applicable, and violations thereof can be enforced (54).

In Switzerland, the mobility rights of persons with disabilities are addressed through various legislative measures, even though the Swiss federal constitution does not explicitly recognize an independent fundamental right to mobility (55). While the constitution guarantees personal mobility in various forms (54), specific provisions for persons with disabilities are outlined in the Disability Equality Act, which was enacted in 2004. This act mandates the adaptation of buildings, structures and public transportation to the needs of persons with disabilities, ensuring their ability to use public transportation independently (56). The responsibility for implementing the DDA is shared among different entities (e.g., cantons, municipalities, transportation companies). Public transportation companies are responsible for the implementation, except for the adjustments to bus stops, which are the responsibility of cantons and municipalities. The federal government supports transportation companies, both organizationally and financially (57). Despite these efforts, the goal of full accessibility was not met by the 2023 deadline, with approximately 40% of Swiss railway stations and two-thirds of bus and tram stops remaining inaccessible (57). This lack of access presents significant challenges for persons with disabilities in using public transportation as evidenced by the Swiss Health Survey 2017. The survey revealed that 30% of persons with severe impairments face difficulties or are unable to use public transportation independently, a contrast to the 1% of persons without disabilities facing similar issues (58). Further, regional analyses within Switzerland, such as those conducted in the cantons of Lucerne (59), Zurich (60,61), and St. Gallen (62), confirmed restrictions in the mobility of persons with disabilities. In conclusion, despite legislative efforts to improve accessibility, the persistent inaccessibility of public transportation remains a significant barrier for persons with disabilities, highlighting the need for more personalized transportation solutions to uphold their human rights.

Paratransit services in Switzerland

One of the personalized transportation options is paratransit services. These are door-to-door transportation services for persons with disabilities, which supplement the public transportation system. However, the per-trip cost of these services can be significantly higher, sometimes up to ten

times more than those of the public transportation options (63). This disparity is exacerbated by the lack of flexible and affordable payment solutions, such as day passes or subscriptions, commonly available for public transportation (64). The financing scheme of paratransit services is complex, with various funding sources covering different trip purposes (64). For example, trips for leisure activities (shopping, hairdresser, cultural and political events, excursions, participation in associations) are mostly subsidized by cantons (64). Nonetheless, these funds may be limited to a certain number of trips per month or restricted according to the income/wealth of persons with disabilities (65,66). Other travel purposes such as school, work, medical appointments are (partially) financed by the confederation's social insurances or benefits such as the disability insurance, health insurances, accident insurance, old age insurance, social assistance, and supplementary benefits (64). Despite this support, there are notable gaps, such as the 50% coverage for trips to medical appointments up to a maximum of 500 CHF, leaving the question of who bears the remaining costs unanswered (64). These costs are often covered by the persons with disabilities (64).

This financing situation is also partly due to the diverse regulations and organization of paratransit services within Switzerland. The responsibility for paratransit services in Switzerland is carried by the cantons, resulting in distinct legal frameworks, if there are any, and, in some cases, they are only valid up to the cantonal border (64). Moreover, there are no regulations for the cantons that make it mandatory to provide a certain number of paratransit services (64). Some cantons like Luzern, Zurich, and Basel have developed specific funding concepts for leisure-related travel (65–68). Several cantons, such as Bern and Zurich, commission organizations with accrediting paratransit service providers, granting authorizations to persons with disabilities, and controlling and accounting for cantonal subsidies (65,66,68,69). For instance, Pro Mobil Zurich is the largest such organization, encompassing 500 paratransit service providers (66). In contrast, a single provider predominates in some regions such as the cantons of Waadt and Solothurn (70,71). Numerous paratransit services are organized by private foundations, often relying on volunteer drivers (67,71–77). These volunteer services usually require advanced booking, have limited driving capacities, and are funded through fares, donations, and occasionally, municipal or cantonal contributions (63). These diverse organizational and financing models of paratransit services contribute to their ambiguous legal status, distinguishing them from both public transportation and traditional taxi services (64). Although the DDA obliges the confederation and cantons to take measures to prevent discrimination against persons with disabilities, this obligation does not extend to paratransit services.

This current situation of paratransit services in Switzerland highlights the need of examining how these services enable persons with disabilities to participate in daily activities on an equal basis. This

examination is significant, given its profound implications for the individuals, society, and the legal frameworks. However, there is a gap in our understanding of the experiences and needs of paratransit service users in Switzerland. The existing national research has largely focused on quality and customer satisfaction surveys. For example, studies have explored customer satisfaction in Zurich (60) and perceptions regarding the service costs in the canton of St. Gallen (62). Additionally, analyses of paratransit services have been conducted by cantons or the managing paratransit organizations (78,79). These analyses included surveys involving staff from facilities such as residential homes and representatives from different organizations and institutions, such as schools for curative education (59,79). These studies highlighted areas for improvement, such as service flexibility, costs, rural access, and integration in public transportation (59). They also emphasized the necessity for clearer definitions and political legitimacy (79). Yet, the personal experiences of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services remain largely unexplored in these reports. Comprehensive reports on the equal treatment of persons with disabilities in Switzerland often rely on surveys of persons with disabilities, but they tend to overlook or only briefly mention paratransit services (80–82).

Besides the research in Switzerland, only a limited number of international studies have explored the experiences of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services. In these studies, paratransit services are only a part of broader transportation issues. These studies underlined the significant role of paratransit services in enhancing well-being and social interaction, as evidenced in Canada (83), and also highlighted the challenges, such as high costs, faced by users in the United States (84). Bascom and Christensen (15) investigated the impact of limited transportation options on social participation in the United States. Their findings indicated that individuals with vision impairments were the predominant users of paratransit services, and the presence of a social network influenced its utilization. Meanwhile, Sitter and Mitchell (30) specifically focused on paratransit services in their photo voice study with five participants in eastern Canada, revealing that while paratransit services facilitated social and familial connections, users faced challenging issues such as long waiting times, diminished spontaneity, and lack of services in certain areas. In conclusion, the national and international knowledge gap regarding the experiences of paratransit users underscores the need for more in-depth research to fully understand and address their mobility challenges and the influence of using paratransit services on participation in daily activities.

In summary, transportation is essential for the participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities and for promoting their health and well-being. In Switzerland, despite legislative efforts, significant barriers in public transportation persist, which underscores the need for paratransit services. However, these services have a complex funding situation and regional disparities influencing access. The legal

framework addresses mobility rights of persons with disabilities but lacks specificity for paratransit services. The literature addressing how this situation of paratransit services impact the participation of persons with disabilities in daily activities often lacks perspectives from the individuals themselves or does not consider the specific context of Switzerland. Investigating this situation is important for understanding the specific challenges and needs of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services in Switzerland so that we as society can improve their access to and experience with these services, their participation in daily activities, well-being, health and to fulfil fundamental human rights.

OBJECTIVES AND SPECIFIC AIMS

The overall objectives of my thesis are to examine the experiences of persons with disabilities with paratransit services in Switzerland and to explore how these services influence their participation in daily activities.

To achieve the overall objectives, the thesis focuses on three specific aims:

- 1/ Examining the experiences and needs of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services in Switzerland.
- 2/ Identifying the impact of paratransit services on participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities in Switzerland.
- 3/ Assessing the impact of per-trip costs and financing schemes for paratransit services in Switzerland on the participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the research design and its rationale and provides an overview of the three studies' methodologies, ethical considerations, and the context of the thesis.

Research design and rationale

We chose a mixed-method exploratory sequential design, which combines inductive and deductive processes (85). Initially, we explored the topic qualitatively, which was followed by the development of a context-specific survey for quantitative testing as described by Creswell and Plano Clark (86). Our selection of the mixed-method exploratory sequential design is based on the following considerations: 1) Context-specific questionnaire: After reviewing the literature, we discovered that no context-specific questionnaire was available to investigate the experiences and needs of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services in Switzerland. Given the unique legal and organizational structure of paratransit services in Switzerland and the rights of persons with disabilities (as influenced by Swiss and international law), a context-specific questionnaire became essential to address the topic. 2) Inductive exploration: We initially explored the phenomenon inductively (Study I), employing a constructivist view and a qualitative method. According to Adom (87), the constructivist view "asserts that reality is subjective" and can only be regarded from "the individual perspective". This view was suitable to reveal the diversity of the subjective realities of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services (87). This diversity manifests itself in the interrelationships of the individual impairment with environmental factors (e.g., social support, socio-economic status, or accessibility of transportation modes) of persons with disabilities and the variability of ordering, using, and financing paratransit services throughout Switzerland. 3) Qualitative results informed our quantitative inquiry: The qualitative investigation in Study I informed the subsequent development of a quantitative survey (Studies II + III). We moved from the constructivist to the postpositivist view in generalizing the qualitative results. This approach is used to "explore the phenomena objectively with the help of [...] qualitative data" (88). This allowed us to investigate the experiences and needs of persons with disabilities objectively but not losing the subjective perspective of these persons, gained in the qualitative part of the design.

Outline of studies

Three interrelated studies contribute to the objectives and aims of my thesis. Whereas Study I investigates the experiences of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services in Switzerland overall, Studies II and III focus more specifically on the effects of paratransit service factors on participation in the daily activities of persons with disabilities.

Study I (Chapter 2) addresses the first aim of the thesis and 1) investigates the experiences and needs of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services in Switzerland and 2) analyses how barriers and facilitators in using paratransit services influence participation in the daily activities of persons with disabilities. We led five focus group discussions. This qualitative approach was suggested by Gibbs (89) and Barbour (90) in a mixed-method sequential design to collect valuable information through interaction and exchange. Our participants were 31 adults (aged 18 and above) with and without disabilities (physical, visual, cognitive) who either used paratransit services themselves or had relatives who did. We analyzed the data from the focus group discussion using qualitative content analysis as described by Mayring (91).

Study II (Chapter 3) aligns with the second aim of the thesis and investigates the effects of paratransit service factors on dissatisfaction with the participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities in Switzerland. We conducted a national cross-sectional study using an online questionnaire with a focus on the experiences and needs of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services in Switzerland. Due to the absence of a suitable questionnaire, Creswell and Plano Clark (85) recommend developing a new one based on the results of a qualitative study. Following this recommendation, we developed our questionnaire on the basis of the results of our initial qualitative study, adhering to the survey methodologies described by Philipps et al. (92) and Wolf et al. (93). We collected data from 536 participants (aged 18 and above) with disabilities (walking, sensory, mental, cognitive, communication) across three language regions in Switzerland. We analyzed the data with quantitative methods using descriptive and regression analysis as described by Field et al. (94). The dependent variable was dissatisfaction with activities and participation. Independent variables were different paratransit service factors such as the frequency of use, ordering in advance, spontaneous use, availability, safety, costs, pickup location, and accompaniment after the ride. We hypothesized that factors of paratransit services affect dissatisfaction with participation in daily activities.

Study III (Chapter 4) contributes to the third aim of the thesis. This study investigates how the per-trip costs and financing scheme of paratransit services affect dissatisfaction with participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities in Switzerland. This study used the same data collection as Study II but with a focus on the cost and financing schemes of paratransit services. We analyzed the data of the 536 participants using quantitative methods including descriptive and inferential statistics (multiple correspondence analysis, LASSO- and regression analysis). The dependent variable was dissatisfaction with activities and participation. Independent variables included cost and financing scheme factors of paratransit services such as activity-related financing, subsidies, costs, cancellations due to costs, or

frequency of use in light of the costs. We hypothesized that the per-trip costs and financing schemes of paratransit services increase dissatisfaction with participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities in Switzerland.

Ethical considerations

We considered relevant ethical questions for all three studies. Participants signed an informed consent sheet, which provided information about the study’s aims and objectives, voluntary participation, and the right to refuse or withdraw without consequences. Additionally, potential participants were informed about the benefits and risks of participation. Throughout each study, the research team maintained confidentiality and secrecy about the data. The data was stored on a secure server at the ZHAW. Only two researchers had access to this server. The research team designed and conducted all studies in such a way that the risk of harm from participation was always low and acceptable to the participants. The studies were submitted in advance to the Zurich Cantonal Ethics Committee, which certified its non-responsibility (BASEC no. Req-2021-00257).

Thesis context

My thesis forms part of the project «Equal Mobility through Paratransit Services?» undertaken by the University of Applied Sciences ZHAW, the University of Lucerne and the Foundation Disability Transport Canton of Bern BTB (see Figure 1). The project was financed by the Federal Office for the Equality of Persons with Disabilities EBGB, Pro Infirmis and BTB (63).

Figure 1

Project structure “Equal Mobility through Paratransit Services?” with Studies of the Thesis

Note. Project duration from February 2021 to February 2024.

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CHAPTER 2

The experiences and needs of persons with disabilities in using paratransit services

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CHAPTER 3

Use of paratransit services and its effect on dissatisfaction with activities and participation for persons with disabilities

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CHAPTER 4

Cost and financing of paratransit services and their effect on dissatisfaction with participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities

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CHAPTER 5

Discussion

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The overall objectives of this thesis were to examine the experiences of persons with disabilities with paratransit services in Switzerland and to explore how these services influence their participation in daily activities. The results of Study I showed that paratransit services often contribute to participation in daily activities of persons with disabilities by facilitating factors such as safety, driver support and door-to-door services. In contrast, a key finding of my thesis is that barriers, such as high per-trip costs, lead to inaccessible transportation and negatively affect the participation of some persons with disabilities in leisure activities. This negative effect of inaccessible transportation on participation has been captured in the concept of transport-related social exclusion (1–5). As defined in the introduction of this thesis, transport-related social exclusion is the process of transport disadvantage leading to social exclusion (3,6–8). Our Study I demonstrates that barriers to using paratransit services are perceived as transport disadvantage to persons with disabilities. Furthermore, the results of all three studies in this thesis lead to the observation that reliance on paratransit services may make some persons with disabilities to experience social exclusion, thus facing transport-related social exclusion. To elaborate on the foundation for this observation, I will discuss our results in light of the four characteristics of social exclusion as described by Bak (9) and Morgan et al. (10). First, their characteristic of multidimensionality includes various vulnerability factors such as unemployment, poverty, and health issues, all of which can contribute to social exclusion. Second, their characteristic of non-participation examines whether persons with disabilities experience a lack of participation in social, political, and cultural activities. Third, Bak (9) and Morgan et al. (10) observe that, due to the dynamic nature of underlying processes of social exclusion, it evolves over time. In our context, this means that factors affecting the use of paratransit services can change over time, thereby altering the impact of these services on social exclusion. Finally, the multiple-level aspect highlights that social exclusion affects and occurs at individual, community, institutional, and federal levels (9,10). These characteristics collectively prevent persons with disabilities from participating in daily activities (7).

Multidimensionality of social exclusion

In all three of our studies, a portion of our study population demonstrated the multidimensionality of social exclusion by facing challenges such as low income, unemployment, mental and physical health impairments, inaccessibility to public transportation, or lack of social support. Accordingly, the ICF model shows how a multitude of factors can impact health (11). Therefore, it is reasonable to deduce that the more dimensions lead to social exclusion, the higher the likelihood that persons with disabilities will face health issues. Health issues stemming from transport-related social exclusion include stress, depression, and poor physiological functioning (12). One of the most direct consequences of transport-

related social exclusion on health is the inaccessibility of healthcare (13). According to the Federal Statistical Office (14), persons with disabilities were four times more likely to forgo medical appointments than those without disabilities. The significant value of medical appointments is further evidenced by our study results. Our survey's analysis showed that 21% of the study population (n = 536) deliberately refrained from participation in daily activities because of paratransit service costs (15). Of them, 8% refrained from travelling to medical appointments (15), and the results of Study III underscored that foregoing medical appointments raises dissatisfaction of persons with disabilities. Building on the understanding of how the multidimensionality of social exclusion impacts health and participation, I will discuss how barriers in using paratransit services contribute to the non-participation of persons with disabilities in daily activities.

Non-participation of social exclusion

In Study I, we identified several barriers, such as the unavailability of services, which hinder the use of paratransit services and lead to non-participation among persons with disabilities. This finding aligns well with other studies showing a negative relationship between participation in daily activities and the use of paratransit services (16–19). However, unlike Study I, the results of Studies II and III do not clearly indicate whether barriers to using paratransit services prevented the persons with disabilities from participating in daily activities. While in these studies we have identified certain aspects of paratransit services that contribute to dissatisfaction with participation in daily activities, it remains unclear whether dissatisfaction can be equated with non-participation and, by extension, social exclusion. Furthermore, Bak (9) questions whether social exclusion is a subjective experience or an objective condition. Following Imms et al. (20), who defined participation as encompassing both attendance and the feeling of involvement in activities, I infer that dissatisfaction may lead to a perceived lack of involvement and with it serving as an indicator of non-participation and social exclusion.

Another factor contributing to non-participation and, consequently, social exclusion are high transportation costs. The literature has demonstrated the negative impact of high transportation costs broadly and some studies have focused on the financial burden of operational costs on paratransit service providers (21–25). However, all studies in my thesis establish the impact of the high per-trip costs of paratransit services on persons with disabilities. Moreover, our results suggest that the current Swiss system for covering these costs may not adequately support participation in daily activities for persons with disabilities. This is also shown by the results of our survey, which revealed that 59% (n = 536) of persons with disabilities would use paratransit services more frequently if the costs were comparable to those of public transportation (15). Notably, 72% of participants in Studies II and III reported household incomes below 50 000 CHF, which is below the median income of Swiss households

(26). However, this number may not be entirely accurate, as the survey did not specify what constituted household income, leaving the components included in these calculations unclear. Nevertheless, according to the Federal Statistical Office, 16% of persons with disabilities live with an income below the Swiss median, compared to 10% of those without disabilities (14). Thus, the high per-trip cost of paratransit services – which can be up to ten times more expensive than public transportation for equivalent distances – becomes a substantial burden (27). This disparity leads to inequality and constitutes a violation of human rights (28).

Few studies have addressed the direct experiences of persons with disabilities concerning the high costs of paratransit services and their impact on participation. Sitter and Mitchell (29) emphasize that costs become a significant burden for persons with disabilities when subsidized paratransit options are not available, leaving much more expensive alternatives, such as taxis, as the only option. This observation aligns with our survey results, where 27% of the participants (n = 536) lacked access to sufficient subsidized trips (15). Furthermore, the results of Study I reveal how the sufficiency of subsidies varies depending on factors such as the individual's health conditions, weather conditions, and the specific activities for which the paratransit service is used. Jeekel (2018) argues that the lack of monetary resources is not the primary reason that persons with disabilities experience transport disadvantages. This view may hold some merit, considering the various transportation barriers that persons with disabilities face, such as the inaccessibility of public transportation or the lack of support. High paratransit service per-trip costs represent just one aspect of these challenges. However, the per-trip costs and the financing of these trips can determine whether a trip is possible for individuals who rely solely on paratransit services. As such, it plays a significant role in transport-related social exclusion. Our results also confirm the findings of previous literature (30,31) that another barrier in using transportation leading to non-participation is the limited number of paratransit services available and their inflexibility in scheduling and usage.

Dynamic nature of social exclusion

Besides the non-participation of social exclusion, our results, especially from Study I, underscored the dynamic nature of social exclusion. The demand for paratransit services is shaped by various dynamic personal and environmental factors such as health status, access to public transportation, and support from social networks. These factors can change over time, thereby altering the need for paratransit services and the extent to which barriers to their use contribute to social exclusion. Therefore, the dynamic transportation needs of persons with disabilities necessitate dynamic transportation services. Paratransit services could play a crucial role in meeting these individual needs. Previous literature has already described the value and contributions of personalized services to the participation in the daily

activities of persons with disabilities (29,32). My thesis reveals the potential dynamics of paratransit services: the results of Study I identify supportive factors at the executive level (e.g., availability, flexibility in ordering and usage) and at the organizational level (e.g., ensuring supply meets demand with consideration for regional specificities such as rural vs. urban areas, intercantonal organization) to address the dynamic needs. Although paratransit services may address all dynamic needs, Study I shows that these services can still lead to the experiences of non-participation and consequently to transport-related social exclusion. This occurs, for example, when individuals cannot share the same transportation mode as their friends or the general public during paratransit service trips. Understanding the dynamic nature of social exclusion, as influenced by personal and environmental factors, it is important to address the multiple levels that impact the use of paratransit services and by extension, the participation of persons with disabilities in daily activities.

Multiple-levels of social exclusion

My thesis establishes that social exclusion in the context of using paratransit services is influenced at multiple levels: individual, community, institutional, and federal. Each level plays a role in determining whether paratransit services facilitate or hinder participation in the daily activities of persons with disabilities, thus either preventing or contributing to social exclusion. For instance, cantons that subsidize leisure trips and social insurance schemes that help fund medical trips may actively prevent social exclusion. Conversely, as our studies showed, these levels can also be experienced as restrictive when relying on paratransit services, not fitting the transportation needs of persons with disabilities and contributing to social exclusion. This occurs, for example, when the cost coverage limit set by the health insurance company is exceeded or when the number of subsidies is insufficient. Additionally, the lack of a federal legal framework and consistent cantonal policies on financing and offering of paratransit services make these services less accessible to some persons with disabilities, thereby exacerbating social exclusion. When institutional and federal levels fail to provide reliable and affordable paratransit services, the burden shifts to individuals and their networks to overcome these barriers. If they cannot, transport-related social exclusion may ensue.

In summary, although paratransit services generally facilitate the participation of persons with disabilities in daily activities, our results related to the four characteristics of social exclusion – non-participation, multidimensionality, dynamics, multiple-level – indicate that some persons with disabilities in Switzerland who rely on paratransit services exhibit these characteristics. Consequently, it is likely that these individuals experience transport-related social exclusion.

Transport-related social exclusion in leisure activities

As previously noted, my thesis shows that barriers to using paratransit services significantly impact participation in leisure activities and contribute to transport-related social exclusion. The World Leisure Organization (33) defines leisure activities as those which “occur during leisure time”, which is “time relatively free of such commitments as paid or unpaid work or personal maintenance”. Research indicates a general increase in time spent on leisure activities (34), and transportation plays a crucial role in enabling participation in these activities. Data from the Federal Statistical Office (35), reveals that the Swiss population travels primarily for leisure activities, and Cole et al. (36) found that accessible transportation boosts motivation for leisure travel, whereas its inaccessibility reduces it. Moreover, disparities in access to leisure activities, often linked to financial constraints, are rising (34). This is in line with the results of this thesis, showing that gaps in the financing scheme of paratransit services lead to reduced participation in leisure activities. Furthermore, our survey’s analysis showed that 44% of survey respondents (n = 536) reported skipping leisure activities because of transportation issues (15). Park et al. (32) also observed that persons with disabilities make 10–30% fewer trips than those without, particularly for non-work-related travel.

However, Study III identifies some uncertainty about the significance of leisure activities related to transportation for persons with disabilities. Our results suggest that the cancellation of trips for work, medical appointments, and shopping might have a greater impact on dissatisfaction with participation in daily activities than missing leisure activities, even though these results were not statistically significant. This result could be due to the immediate and noticeable consequences of missing essential activities. For instance, persons with disabilities often encounter greater challenges in securing and maintaining employment compared to those without disabilities (37–39), making the cancellation of employment not only difficult to compensate but also carrying significant financial and psychological consequences (40). Additionally, essential tasks such as shopping for food and hygienic products are crucial for fulfilling human needs.

On the other hand, missing leisure activities might have more subtle effects. Some leisure activities, such as meeting friends, can be enjoyed in various places, while others can be substituted with different activities that do not require transportation. This adaptability may prevent an immediate loss of leisure activity opportunities. We also observed a related phenomenon during Study I, where participants appeared to adapt to and accept their limited transportation options and participation in leisure activities. Such adaptations align with existing theories such as the psychological adaptation theory, which posits that environmental barriers shape the coping strategies and responses of persons with disabilities (41–44).

The participation of persons with disabilities in leisure activities is desired from various sides. It is widely recognized as a fundamental right. The CRPD mandates full societal participation (45), and the Swiss DDA provides frameworks to support these rights (46). Moreover, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (47) explicitly mentions the right to leisure activities in Article 7(d) and cultural participation in Article 15. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (48) furthers this in Article 27, advocating for the right to “freely participate in the cultural life of the community [...]” which includes music, sport, and the arts (33). The World Leisure Organization’s Charter (33) elaborates on these rights, urging governments to ensure community access to leisure facilities and services (Art. 7). The CRPD (49) further specifies these rights, compelling states to facilitate participation in recreational, cultural, and sporting activities for persons with disabilities (Art. 30).

Besides the legal obligations, participation in leisure activities of persons with disabilities enriches not only them but also society. For example, leisure activities enables the fulfillment of democratic rights and responsibilities (e.g., voting) (50) and encourages diversity in social groups, which enhances creativity and innovation (51). Furthermore, participation in society, particularly in meaningful leisure activities, is important for health and well-being (52–55). The World Leisure Organization (33) emphasizes the importance of leisure activities for health and well-being through physical activity, cultural engagement and sport.

Another aspect of the participation in leisure activities is economic. Making transportation accessible for all is a highly cost-intensive undertaking, but achieving this goal may also impact costs in other sectors, such as increased healthcare expenditure on mental health issues and higher home care costs due to reduced mobility and social exclusion (56–58). Furthermore, leisure activities, including tourism, make a substantial contribution to Switzerland’s economic output. Tourism encompasses culture, sports, entertainment and dining, all significant to value creation (59,60). Accessible transportation is a prerequisite for touristic consumption among the whole society, including persons with disabilities, the elderly, and families with children.

Strengths and limitations

My thesis presents strengths and limitations. One strength pertains to the diversity of study participants. The experience of using paratransit services to participate in daily activities varies widely across individuals. To capture this individuality, we included a heterogenous sample based on impairments, age, gender, living environment, and job activities, making the results representative in terms of diversity. This approach enabled the investigation of the individuality of the experiences while also recognizing commonalities. Another strength of my thesis is the choice of the research design. Our research showed that the use of paratransit services is context sensitive. The sequential exploratory research design selected for this thesis was an effective choice to take this context sensitivity into account. Another strength of the chosen design is that we could enhance credibility as described by Vivek (61) in using different methods for data collection (methods triangulation) to represent the participants' experiences accurately. This design also supported the development of a new context-sensitive survey. However, a limitation could be that this survey was not tested for reliability and validity before implementation. Another limitation of my thesis arises from the composition of the study population. All three studies included persons that use or have used paratransit services. The voice of persons with disabilities not using paratransit services is missing and could have brought further aspects into the results. Another limitation of this thesis is that it relies on the concepts of participation and disability which are measured by the subjective experiences of persons with disabilities. This subjective approach should be taken into account when transferring the results to different cultural and political contexts.

Conclusion

By analyzing the impact of paratransit services in Switzerland on participation in daily activities from the perspective of persons with disabilities, my thesis demonstrates that paratransit services have positive and negative impacts on the participation of persons with disabilities in daily activities. A positive impact arises if these services meet the needs of persons with disabilities and if the individuals are not solely dependent on paratransit services, having other transportation modes available, such as public transportation, or transportation services provided by family and friends. Conversely, a negative impact emerges because of barriers to using these services, such as high per-trip costs. These barriers are most restrictive for individuals solely dependent on paratransit services. They limit their participation, particularly in leisure activities, which can lead to transport-related social exclusion and violate fundamental human rights.

My thesis establishes a knowledge base for stakeholders and persons with disabilities affected by the state of paratransit services in Switzerland. Stakeholders include government bodies at community, cantonal, and federal levels, politicians, public transportation and paratransit service providers. Based on the results from the three studies, I would like to recommend enhancements such as:

- spontaneous paratransit services in order and use,
- different paratransit service providers available,
- equal per-trip costs comparable to public transportation,
- national coordination and organization of paratransit services, including low-threshold information, ordering, and payment processes while maintaining effective regional service solutions,
- coordination and clarification of financing scheme to meet the individual activity needs of persons with disabilities, offering options comparable to those available to persons without disabilities,
- establishment of a legal framework for paratransit services in Switzerland to ensure regulated and fair transportation for persons with disabilities, as suggested by Gantschnig et al. (27) and
- integration of paratransit services into the public transportation system, which could benefit from existing public transportation tools like subscriptions, national coordination, and accessible ordering and payment solutions.

Not only does my thesis suggest specific improvements at the legal, organizational, and operational levels of paratransit services, but it also stresses the importance of including persons with disabilities to enhance accessible and inclusive transportation. Consequently, it is essential that persons with

disabilities are integral to travel demand modelling, transportation planning, and policy making (32). The complexity of inclusive transportation and its significant impact on the participation of persons with disabilities in daily activities necessitates a collaborative approach. Researchers from health, economic, political, and social sciences as well as from the technical fields must collaborate to adjust or develop new and practical transportation solutions. Future research could investigate the value and desire of the participation in leisure activities and the associated challenges of using transportation for persons with disabilities. Additionally, future studies should focus on the methods of making paratransit services and public transportation more inclusive, ensuring that persons with disabilities can be fully engaged in their use.

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